

DEATH VERSUS NON-EXISTENCE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE ONTOLOGICAL STATUS OF GOD IN NIETZSCHE AND SARTRE

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Abstract:

This paper examines in a comparative manner the death of God in Friedrich Nietzsche and the non-existence of God in Jean-Paul Sartre. As an undertone, it attempts to address man's self-denials, alienation and failure to assert his freedom and independence which was occasioned by his over-reliance on the God-thesis; a situation where every human problem is being interpreted in terms of a divine determinist who had predestined every human experience. Nietzsche found in the Athenian and German cultures the Dionysian spirit required to restore the freedom of Dasein, while Sartre adopted the French revolutionary consciousness and spirit of freedom to address this problem. The death of God in Nietzsche means the death of belief in the God-thesis, the rejection of determinism or fixed principles and the birth of, freedom or superman. On the other hand, Sartre's non-existence of God is a demonstration of the absolute freedom of for-itself and the absence of a creative God who creates essences. Our analysis shows that though there are some cosmetic and structural differences in terms of terminology and logical structure of their arguments, the content and intent of their works as it relates to the subject of discourse are essentially the same; hence they are grouped together as atheistic existentialists. Our work adopts the content cum textual- analytic methods of study.

Key Concepts: God, Dasein, For-itself, Death, Existence, Freedom, God-thesis, Superman, Non-God-thesis

Introduction

One of the most absurd, uncharitable, blasphemous and irrationally rational statements to be made by a for-itself or Dasein is the statement "God is dead" or "God does not exist". Such a Dasein certainly will be blacklisted and libeled with some uncomplimentary titles like madman, fool and atheist as in the case of St. Anselm who believes that "the fools say in their hearts there is no God". If such for-itself is a vote seeker, then we predict that he or she will fail elections even before contesting. If he/she is a trader, then it is as good as predicting that his/her stock will pay for that statement. No matter the social status of such Dasein, it is psychologically axiomatic that society will bless him/her with some social stigmas that are worse than those health stigmas of Ebola and HIV/AIDS. We dare to prophecy further that all the religious institutions around such for-itself will receive another great commission. This time it will be go ye into the world and preach my gospel teaching them that that for-itself is mad, stupid and above all an anti-Christ, therefore flee from him/her.

This stigma and deviant libel has made it very difficult for for-itself to muster the courage, criticalities and skeptical isms required to examine the God-thesis

with an objective consciousness; since it is in the nature of Dasein to seek for praise and fame rather than rejection. The consequence therefore is that the God-thesis continues to dominate the literary world and by extension the human mind. Dasein therefore continues to develop deeper passions and appetite for the God-thesis without applying reason to moderate their defects and excesses. However, despite the magnitude of emotional and social rejection and libels, philosophers remain duty bound as we took the unstated oath to act for the sake of duty and not according to duty. This is perhaps the reason Nietzsche could not be cowed, as he confronted the God-thesis headlong by announcing the death of God, even though we admit that these religious and social libels made serious negative imprints on people's perception of his person. Nietzsche has argued earlier that "My vital instincts turned against ethics and founded a radical counter doctrine slanted esthetically to oppose the Christian libel on life" (Tragedy, 11). Sartre aonetime Nobel laureate also in a bid to restore the freedom of for-it-selves from the deterministic caves of religious institutions, declared the non-existence of God.

Since it is statutorily our “duty sake” as philosophers to examine all issues objectively irrespective of the controversial and dogmatic nature of such subject matter, we attempt in this paper to examine Nietzsche’s conception of the death of God and Sartre’s negation of the existence of God. In other words, the difficult task of this paper is to critically examine in a comparative manner the death of God in Friedrich Nietzsche and the non-existence of God in Jean-Paul Sartre. As a critique of atheistic philosophies, of Nietzsche and Sartre, this work seeks further to show the implications of their philosophies for the independence, autonomy and freedom of Dasein; for the truism and falsehood of the statements “God is dead” and “God does not exist” lies not in the person, nature and hobby of the speaker or writer as the argumentum ad Hominem ad tu quoque avails us, but as James and his co-pragmatists would have it “the cash value”. That is, the practical difference the statements “God is Dead” and “God does not exist” harbors for humanity. Since this work is not intended to be a history of atheism or theism but merely to illuminate the atheistic ideas of Nietzsche and Sartre, we shall now limit our ink by turning to discuss Nietzsche’s idea of the death of God.

A Prelude to the Death of God in Nietzsche

For most people, it is ironical to imagine that Nietzsche who was born into a Christian family with both father and grand-father as Lutheran ministers and professed the Christian faith early in his life could later become one of the greatest atheists and critics of the Christian faith who announced the death of God. But we absolve the shock by admitting the statement “everything is possible”. After all, even the Christian bible admits that everything is possible except that it begins with the caveat “with God”. In fact, we add; with man all things are possible. As early as 1872 when he published *The Birth of Tragedy*, Nietzsche has started manifesting the Aristotelian potentialities of an atheist. Although with a different theme and focus, he examined the Greek conception of gods with particular emphasis on Apollo and Dionysus. Apollo is the soothsaying god of all plastic powers who reigns over the illusion of our inner world of fantasy” (Nietzsche, *Tragedy*, 21). It “was the symbol of order restraint and form”. On the other hand, Dionysus represents the dynamic chain of life which brakes every limits and barriers (Stumpf and Fieser, 381). Nietzsche in his *Twilight of the Idols* explains it thus: Affirmation of life even in its strangest inexhaustibility through the sacrifice of its highest types – that is what I called Dionysian, that is what I recognize as the bridge to the psychology of the tragic poet” (110). “I know of no more exalted symbolism than the Greek symbolism of the Dionysian” (110). Vincent P. Miceli, S. J. differentiates them thus: “Handsome Apollo, the god of plastic arts, symbolizes the Creative luminosity and order of being;

his highest achievement is breathing forms of Titan heroes into chaos. Dionysus, the god of music and bacchanalian delirium, symbolizes universal, unharnessed energy whose invisible surge constructs and destroys universes” (48). These two gods formed the category of meaningfulness and existence for the Greeks. However, it is obvious from Nietzsche’s words that the Greek Olympian gods were mere artistic creatures constructed to enable Dasein to consummate their existence. As Nietzsche puts it: “Now the Olympian magic mountain opens itself before us, it’s very root. The Greeks were keenly aware of the terrors and horrors of existence; in order to be able to live at all they had to place before them the shining fantasy of the Olympians.... In order to live at all the Greeks had to construct these deities” (*Tragedy*, 29-30). Again, the regular use of the expression “illusion” in reference to Apollo as we may see in the statement: “Homer must be viewed as a complete victory of Apollonian illusion” (Nietzsche, *Tragedy*, 31) clearly shows that Nietzsche will certainly come to a point where he will openly negate the existence of God. And the constant importation of the expression “*Principium individuationis*” goes a long way to show the high value Nietzsche has for the individual person and his independence/freedom. He argues that when we confront the Olympians with a different religion in search of love, spirituality and kindness we receive total disappointment as we are faced with an artistic culture which deifies good and bad differently. As we have stated earlier by then Nietzsche had not actualized the full potentials of an atheist, but reading in-between the lines of his work *The Birth of Tragedy*, we understand that Nietzsche had no exalted stool for the gods or any God-figure. It could be deduced that he had a penchant for securing human freedom; hence, adopts the core features of Dionysus which includes its dynamic spirit, as the sure mark of achieving the superman thesis which finally became one of the quiddities of his philosophy. Nietzsche is indeed opposed to any system of fixed principle, in fact, he repudiates Socrates, Plato and Descartes for introducing foundationalism, and normative ethics or secular morality into philosophy and eulogizes Heraclitus and Pythagoras for their radical Dionysian philosophical thoughts and tragic art works. “If men are to cure the blight that already corrodes their culture, then Dionysus must be chosen over Socrates” (Miceli, 49). To the best of our understanding, the idea “God is Dead” which he later dramatically popularized in the *Gay Science* and emphasized in *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* and *The Anti-Christ* was first mooted (even though mute) in *The Birth of Tragedy*. Just take a critical look at the succeeding citation:

Now the slave emerges as a freeman; all the rigid, hostile walls which either necessity or despotism has erected between men are shattered. Now that the gospel of universal harmony is sounded,

each individual becomes not only reconciled to his fellow but actually at one with him-as though the veil of Maya had been torn apart and there remained only shreds floating before the vision of mystical oneness (Nietzsche, *Tragedy*,23).

What then is the implication of the foregoing citation? Nietzsche had grown up in a German society where religion particularly the Christian faith played significant roles in people's assessment of values. He juxtaposes it with the Greek Athenian society which also witnessed a surge of religion and imprisonment of the freedom of Dasein. Recall that Nietzsche was writing in an age when Darwinian evolutionary philosophy that negates divine creationism and affirms Natural Selection had dominated libraries and Schopenhauer *World as Representation* was making its marks in the German intellectual world. Nietzsche following what the above philosophers bequeathed on him, joined in the mission to rescue humanity from the shackles of religious enslavement since it was obvious that Dasein were enslaved by what he later called nihilistic religions—“That the highest values devalue themselves” (Nietzsche *Will*, 9) or Maya as shown in the citation above which connotes the power to do some things beyond the capacity of for-it-selves. Dasein or for-itself therefore needs to liberate himself from these religious caves by recognizing the harmony in nature. This in our analysis implies the death of God as the idea of a great beyond, must give way for Dasein to look inward for the development of his or her full potentials. All the systems of moral judgments must give way for the superman to emerge.

The Death of God in Nietzsche

The idea of death of God in Nietzsche is one of the most misconstrued if not the most misconstrued concepts in the history of philosophy. This is partly due to the rigorous, disjointed and controversial nature of his thoughts, and partly due to the dogmatic and forceful nature of religion which has made it possible for most scholars to interpret it to suit their course of action. The idea of death of God runs through virtually all the works of Nietzsche that we could sustainably argue that the death of God is a central theme in Nietzsche's philosophy. However, it is prominent and direct to the point in few of his works namely *The Gay Science*, *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, and *The Anti-Christ*. In *The Gay Science* Nietzsche argues that “after Buddha was dead they still showed his shadows in a cave for centuries – a tremendous gruesome shadow. God is dead; but given the way people are, there may still for Millenia be caves in which they show his shadow – and we must still defeat his shadow as well” (108). Here Nietzsche attempts to liken the death of God to the death of Buddha who his

followers preserved his shadow for their memory but maintains that God is dead and no memory of his should be preserved. Moving forward Nietzsche dramatically announced the death of God thus:

Haven't you heard of that madman who in the bright morning lit a lantern and ran around the market place crying incessantly, I'm looking for God; I'm looking for God! Since many of those who did not believe in God were standing around together. Just then he caused great laughter. Has he been lost, then? Asked one. Did he lose his way like a child? Asked another or is he hiding? Is he afraid of us? Has he gone to sea? Emigrated? Thus, they shouted laughed, one interrupting the other. The madman jumped into their mist then with his eyes. Where is God? He cried; I'll tell you! We have killed him – you and I! We are all his murderers... (Nietzsche, *Gay*, 125)

To grasp and appreciate the message and idea that Nietzsche communicates in the foregoing citation, the following questions and possible answers will help to illuminate the passage. 1. Why did Nietzsche choose to import the imagery of a madman to express his thought on the death of God? 2. Why was the said madman looking for God with a Lantern and in a market place? 3. Why did the madman decide to stop at the point where many unbelievers of the God-thesis were standing? 4. Why did the madman say we have killed God or how are we all the murderers of God? As to the first question, the imagery of a madman that Nietzsche imported to communicate his idea of the death of God in the said citation is key, it is synonymous with the imagery of a drunk. The madman is someone that often says the truth but the society does not take him seriously as he is said to be insane. Nietzsche may have imported this imagery for two reasons first, to express the idea that though God is dead, society does not know or take it seriously and secondly to avoid or reduce the attacks on his person if he directly claims that God is dead without importing the image of a madman. However, we can still argue that Nietzsche could not achieve the second aim as we can sustainably argue that the whole saga and libel of insanity allegedly suffered by Nietzsche was largely due to his importation of the madman's imagery, as those opposed to his idea of the death of God simply dismissed him as a madman. Our response to the second question is that by using the Lantern to look for God, Nietzsche probably was demonstrating the fact that God is not a spatio-temporal object hence, there is no need for spatio-temporal entities like man to rely on non-spatio-temporal entities like God for their existence. As

for the second conjunct of the question, the market represents a place where all human entities in particular and all spatio-temporal entities in general converge, interact or visibly carry out their day-to-day activities, so the fact that God could not be found in the market place speaks otherwise of his beingness. In a limited sense it could also represent the meeting of the wicker or lower men. Nietzsche reveals this in *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* when he was addressing the higher men/supermen thus: “You higher men, learn this from me: in the market place no one believes in higher men” (232). On the third question the point must be made that Nietzsche needed to applaud himself and his likes – the atheists and to express the idea that their philosophies had made serious marks as they have successfully killed the idea of God and the God-thesis. The answer to the fourth question is partly imbedded in our answer to the third question and that is the fact that Nietzsche and all atheist alike contributed in killing God by the doubts and level of disbelief their works have created in the minds of human beings and the society at large. However, most theists readers of Nietzsche’s works interpret it from the perspective of Nietzsche’s rejection of moral formalism or Christian normative ethics or nihilistic doctrines. Our interpretation does not invalidate theirs but rather corroborates it, as Nietzsche rejected any system of judgement that attempts to limit for-itself by setting boundaries to what he/she should or ought to do and what he/she should or ought not to do.

Before moving forward in our explication of the death of God in Nietzsche, let us take a pause to expound the point we made earlier in this work – the fact that God whether the (Apollonian, Dionysian, Buddhist or Christian) was a product and creation of the human being. This point we believe will help us to understand the ontological status of God in Nietzsche and to further appreciate what Nietzsche meant by the death of God. In *The Will to Power*, Nietzsche traces the origin of religion or God to man’s psychology/epistemology of suffering/pain. According to him, in a bid to give an epistemic account of his own experiences, man through a psychological process created a God which ordinarily is a psychological personal entity and not an empirico-existential entity. In his words: “those conditions that seemed to him strange, thrilling, overwhelming; he interpreted as obsession and enchantment by the powers of a person (thus the Christian, the most naïve and backward specie of man today, traces hope, repose the feeling of redemption back to psychological inspiration by God” (85). In *Human, All Too Human*, Nietzsche traced the origin of God/religion to fear and need, making God again a psychological product of man born out of fear and need. “For out of fear and need each religion is born, creeping into existence on the byways of reason” (73). It is on this ground that Bertrand Russell one of the chief

critics in philosophy, criticizes Nietzsche. According to him,” It never occurred to Nietzsche that the lust for power, with which he endows his superman, is itself an outcome of fear. Those who do not fear their neighbours see no necessity to tyrannize over them...” (693). However, Nietzsche makes this same point in *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* when he states:

... Oh my brothers, this god that I created was of human make and madness, like all gods! Human he was and only a poor fake of human and ego. From my own ash and ember it came to me, this ghost, and truly! It did not come to me from beyond! What happened, my brothers? I overcame myself, my suffering self, I carried my own ashes to the mountain, I invented a brighter flame for myself and behold! The ghost *shrank* from me! Now it would be suffering and torture for the convalesced one to believe in such ghosts. Now it would be suffering and humiliation. Thus, I speak to the hinterworldly. It was suffering and incapacity that created all hinterworlds, and that brief madness of happiness that only the most suffering person experiences (20).

Having appreciated this point, we now note that when Nietzsche talks of the death of God, he was not talking of the physical death of a being that created and lords over the universe as most Christians may believe. He was not talking of the death of a spatio-temporal God whose abode and throne is in heaven and his legs and foot stool are on earth, but the death of a God which is part of the human person, a God who later became lord over human beings through a psychological process. Man became alienated from his product - God, as he now looks up to God for direction, protection and every other thing. The freedom of Dasein became mortgaged on the altar of the deterministic tendencies of these God. Man’s actions and inactions became a subject of moral judgements using the commandments of these God as the yardstick or standard of measurement and judgements. The death of God in Nietzsche means therefore that belief in God has become unbelievable. “What does the whole world know today?” Asked Zarathustra. Perhaps, that the old God no longer lives, the one in whom the whole world once believed?” “You said it,” answered the old man gloomily. And I served this old God until his final hour” (Nietzsche, Zarathustra, 209). T. Z. Lavine emphasizes this point when he says “By the death of God Nietzsche means the death of our belief in God. It is our belief in God that is dead” (324). It means a total recovery of the powers of man to take responsibility, a total recovery of the freedom

of Dasein. No wonder R. J. Hollingdale in his introductory commentary to Nietzsche's *Twilight of the Idols* and *The Anti-Christ* argues that independence of mind – independence in general is what Nietzsche teaches (7). Indeed, the death of God connotes the birth of superman - (overman or Übermensch). As George de Huszar puts it in his 1945 article "Nietzsche's Theory of Decadence and the Transvaluation of all Values": "Nietzsche saw in the murderer of God the prerequisite for the utmost development of the self. He was pleased neither with God nor with man, and as an alternative invented the superman" (267). In *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* Nietzsche puts it thus:

Before God! – But now this god has died! You higher men, this god was your greatest danger. It is only now, since he lies in his grave, that you are resurrected. Only now the great noon comes, only now the higher man becomes ruler.... Well then! Well now! You higher men! Only now is the mountain in labor with humanity's future. God died: now we want – the overman to live (232).

It means that the God-thesis was an obstacle hindering the full development and actualization of the full potentials of Dasein. Just as the powers of man to assert his freedom died in Wole Soyinka's *The Man Died*, so also the concept of God has killed man and his powers to assert his being. Nietzsche in the *Twilight of the Idols* also makes this point, "The concept 'God' has hitherto been the greatest objection to existence... We deny God; in denying God, we deny accountability: only by doing that do we redeem the world" (54). It is incompatible for God and man to live at the same time, since to be man means to assert one's freedom, responsibility and existence which simply translates to lording over one's self and to be God means to determine and lord over man and other entities. The death of God therefore becomes the emergence of the overman. As may be interpreted in two different ways, the overman now takes the place of God in a man's life (a man over/beyond). First, as we have shown, God is man's product extended beyond or over him. To be overman therefore means to recover the part of man that became God having killed the psychological God. The second sense is to go beyond the imperfections and limitations which many have attributed to the nature of man. Man, therefore becomes stronger, (Superman) with so much will to do and undo. "The Übermensch in *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, is the figure who is successful in becoming his own master. He is an overman, more than a man, a human being that is human and more" (Daigle, 8).

The death of God for Nietzsche therefore implies that man takes over the spiritual space of will and power hitherto occupied by God and begin to perform the celestial roles. Miceli, puts it thus: "...the demise of God and the dissolution of faith in him has promoted man to the overlordship of the universe. Man's creative energies are now released to develop themselves to their unimaginable fullness" (51).

The death of God in Nietzsche also means the death of morality or moral formalism, ontology or circularism. "At the same time, the death of God meant for Nietzsche the opening of a new day – a day when the essentially life-denying ethics of Christianity could be replaced with a life-affirming philosophy" (Stumpf and Fieser, 381). This is exactly the magnum opus of Nietzsche's works *Beyond Good and Evil* and *The Anti-Christ*. In *The Anti-Christ* for example, Nietzsche argues: "One knows my demand of philosophers that they place themselves beyond good and evil – that they have the illusion of moral judgement beneath them" (55). According to him, there are no moral nor religious facts anywhere. It also constitutes one of the major reasons Nietzsche attacked religion in general and Christianity in particular. Christianity as a nihilistic religion had through its prescriptive morality, attempted to weaken human beings through its emphasis on pity, humility, virtue etc. Man could no longer actualize its full potentials and development because of the too many chains and restrictions on him; in the name and guise of religious ethics – thou shall not kill, thou shall not still, thou shall not commit adultery, thou shall not commit fornication, thou shall not have any other God except me and so many other thou shall nots. In fact, the problem with ethics in general and Christian ethics in particular is the assumption that there is a fixed nature, hence there should be a fixed way of behavior. "The fundamental fallacy of the Christian ethics is to him its negation of the individual, its denial of the essentially human" (Warbeke, 373). In *Human, All Too Human*, Nietzsche writes "How gladly one would exchange the false claims of priests – that there is a God who demands the good from us, who is guardian and witness of each act, each moment, each thought, who loves us and wants the best for us in every fortune..." (71). Indeed, for Nietzsche the Christian conception of God is one of the most corrupt conceptions of God, as God is seen as the God of the sick, a spider and spirit (Nietzsche, *Anti-Christ*, 128).

In summary, Nietzsche's Concept of death of God could be reduced to either the death of belief in God and the birth of belief in man, the death of religious determinism and the birth of human freedom, the death of morality or the death of God and the birth of superman.

Non-Existence of God in Jean-Paul Sartre

The same way that Nietzsche attempted to show in virtually all his works that God is dead so also Jean-Paul Sartre attempted to demonstrate the non-existence of God in virtually all his works. Sartre was largely influenced by Nietzsche and others the same way Charles Darwin and Schopenhauer influenced Nietzsche. Yaffa Wolfman who attempted to show the contributions of Goethe's Faust to Sartre's play, *The Devil and the Good Lord* could not negate the fact that Sartre's play was an affirmation of Nietzsche's position that God is dead. In his words: "... despite the echoes of Faust in the play, Sartre is said to have based himself more on Nietzsche's "God is dead" than on Goethe's theme and idea in Faust" (182). Again, in his play *The Flies*, Sartre is said to have presented a hero in the character of Orestes who revolted against the tyrant Gods and killed their human Gauleiters in order to liberate the people (Miceli, 217). In his *Being and Nothingness* which appears to be his greatest work, he did not hesitate to show how the notion of God's existence has put forward the fallacy of essence of for-itself before its existence. Indeed, existence precedes essence. Human beings therefore are simply condemned to be free since God does not exist to create their essences. Although unlike Nietzsche who enjoyed the knowledge of his biological father and grandfather who were both Lutheran ministers, Sartre narrates in his Autobiography – *The Words*, how he had the privilege of being born by a father who died and left no trace of his semblance for his young son and as a result he was bread, buttered, and groomed by his grandfather and grandmother who apparently apart from their seemingly mouth professed Catholic membership were non-theists. What does it mean to exist? Or what is the etymology of the word existence? The word existence was derived from the Latin *existere*, *existerere*, or "existentia" which means to "step out", "stand forth" or be. Therefore, to say God exist is to say he stepped out, stand forth or be. Going by this etymology, it may be easily sustained that God does not exist because almost all theistic concepts of God see God as a being without origin (eternal being). It is in respect of this etymological conception of the nature of God that John H. Hick recalls the words of Paul Tillich thus: "the question of the existence of God can be neither asked nor answered. If asked, it is a question about that which by its very nature is above existence, and therefore the answer – whether negative or affirmative implicitly denies the nature of God. It is atheistic to affirm the existence of God as it is to deny it" (Tillich, cited in Hick, 7-8). He is the first cause or creator. For them therefore God simply is – that is, he is the beginning and the end, hence does not have an origin but is the origin. But we must also mention here that when Sartre talks of the non-existence of God, he was not referring to the mere conceptual God as could be easily validated by the etymological definition, by non-

existence of God he was referring to the non-existence of God in content.

What then does Sartre mean by the non-existence of God? For us, Sartre defended his non-God-thesis from three points of view – namely, rejection of the ontological and cosmological prove of the existence of God by the medieval fathers, the subject-object relationship between God and man, and the affirmation of human freedom and rejection of determinism. Sartre in his famous work *Being and Nothingness* questions both the ontological as well as the cosmological prove or claims by the scholastics of the existence of an in-itself or God which is said to follow logically from the Aristotelian notions of contingency (possibility) and necessity (sufficiency). First of all, he identifies the three traditional conceptions of beings by using his own baked concepts. Beings could be stratified into three, namely: Being in-itself (God), Being for-itself (Human being) and Being for-others (other beings). They could also be seen as the Being of consciousness, the consciousness of For-itself, and the consciousness of others respectively. For Sartre, the attempt by the scholastics to derive the existence of an in-itself from the finite possibilities of for-it-selves/for-others is seriously flawed. This is because there are two ways that we could view the notion of possibility. First, as a "subjective indication" (Show of ignorance or limitation of knowledge) as in the case of the statement "It is possible that Pierre is dead" and second, as an "ontological structure of the real" (the manifestation of the necessity/foundation and properties of being). This second sense strictly refers to the word "God" as used by the medieval fathers. "In this case being sustains its own possibilities in being; it is their foundation, and the necessity of being cannot then be derived from its possibility, in a word, God if he exists, is contingent" (Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, 81). He agrees with Husserl that it is not the role of consciousness either to give being to itself or to receive it from others. "In addition to that, the ontological proof like the cosmological proof fails to establish a necessary being, the explanation and foundation of my being – in so far as I am a particular being cannot be sought in necessary being" (Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, 81). The medieval God therefore does not exist.

In the second sense, Sartre states: "these attempts, which imply the absolute recognition of God as a subject who cannot be an object, carry their own contradiction within them and are always failures" (*Being and Nothingness*, 290). What then is the contradiction? When I posit myself as an object and God as the subject I tend to establish an object-subject relationship not only in the Cartesian sense of Knower-known relationship but also in the religious sense of the created-creator relationship where the created can never know or comprehensively apprehend the epistemic holism of the creator. However,

since God does not exist these subject-object relationship plays out in this manner; “I exist alienated and cause myself to learn from outside what I will be” (Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, 290). The underneath citation may better explain it:

For if God is consciousness, he is integrated in the totality. And if by his nature, he is a being beyond consciousness (that is, an in-itself which would be its own foundation) still the totality can appear to him only as an object (in that case he lacks the totality’s internal disintegration as the subjective effort to reapprehend the self) or as subject (then since God is not this subject, he can only experience it without knowing it). Thus, no point of view on the totality is conceivable; the totality has no “outside,” and the very question of the meaning of the “underside” is stripped of meaning (Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, 302).

As we have noted earlier in the section on Nietzsche, Sartre influenced by Nietzsche implies that the concept of man and God are incompatible “Thus the passion of man is the reverse of Christ, for man loses himself as man in order that God may be born. But the idea of God is contradictory and we lose ourselves in vein” (*Being and Nothingness*, 617). Man has only one desire and that is the desire to be God. This desire can be equated with Nietzsche’s superman. God does not exist because the concept of God is created by man and out of man’s existential need. Note that existence precedes essence – which means that to say God exists would mean that there is first of all an entity called God who existed and thereafter created his essences. But this is not true because even the name and essence of God are creations of man. According to Sartre therefore “Whatever may be the myths and rites of the religion considered, God, is first “sensible to the hearts” of man as the one who identifies and defines him in his ultimate and fundamental project” (*Being and Nothingness*, 566). What this means when we view it from St. Anselm’s perspective where God is defined as the greatest conceivable of all beings or St. Aquinas’ cosmological arguments or even Bishop George Berkeley’s “*esse est percipi*” (to be is to be perceived) principle, is that it is man that must perform the active roles of conceiving, proofing and or perceiving God. This is exactly the point Feuerbach made when he said that human beings and not God are the basic reality. Recall that we had defined God in Sartre as the being of consciousness. It is a value which navigates the relationship between the in-itself and the for-itself.

The third point is that man is condemned to be free. Here as we see in “Existentialism is a Humanism” Sartre argues that if God does exist then human beings or For-itself can’t be free, but one of the core cognitive and evidential categories of humanism is freedom. Human beings are condemned to be free because though they did not create themselves, they must assert their liberty. The existential reality is a reality of freedom. He defines freedom as “nothing other than a choice which creates for-itself its own possibilities” (Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, 566). Again, he explains it further:

Every for-it-self is free choice; each of its acts – the most insignificant as well as the most weighty (Sic) – expresses this choice and emanates from it. This is what we have called our freedom. We have now grasped the meaning of this choice; it is a choice of being, either directly or by the appropriation of the world, or rather by both at once. Thus, my freedom is a choice of being God and all my acts, all my projects translates this choice and reflect it in a thousand and one ways, for there is an infinity of ways of being and of ways of having (Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, 599).

What then does Sartre mean by these project or man’s desire to be God? Man is simply the interpreter of every human experience and he has absolute freedom to interpret his experiences (whether tragic or pleasant) to suit his goal, hence what Christ simply did was to interpret his experience of persecution and crucifixion on the cross to suit his ultimate goal to be God. Every For-it-self reserves the liberty to interpret his experiences. For instance, if it rains on a harvest day, sowing day or any other day of special ceremony like marriage we interpret it to mean a divine blessing of our harvest, seeds or marriage as the case may be, whereas we could have interpreted such rain differently, to mean a divine rejection of our harvest, seed and sacrilege on our marriage. Human beings have the ambition to be God that is why they often interprets their experiences to prove the God-thesis.

For us, Sartre and virtually every other scholar do not appear to understand the concept of freedom as most often they use the word synonymously with “good reason” and that is why most times they argue that every act of freedom goes hand-in-hand with responsibility. But this conception of freedom is limited. The word freedom is an existential reality that seldom manifest in our existential engagements. It is closely associated with courage. That is to say that for us, freedom is the courage

and ability of an individual or for-itself to refuse to be coerced to action or inaction. Freedom has nothing or little to do with good reason. A free action may as well be a foolish action. It is because of this bad faith conception of freedom that scholars find it difficult to invalidate Jonathan Edward's argument that there is a prompting for every free action; which made the American Calvinist refer to arguments for freedom as spurious. Indeed, what prompts could be said to determine. For instance, if Mr. A consults Mr. B to accept an offer to be appointed as the federal minister of petroleum and Mr. B rejects the offer, the prompting for rejecting this offer may merely be the ontological imperative to say no. Yet, we cannot say that Mr. B's action was a free action, however, we may call it a rational action. Why? Because there is no element of force or threat which he resisted. It may be rational or irrational depending on the reason for rejecting the offer. On the other hand, if an armed robber or a group of armed robbers at gun point orders a man to have sex with his mother or daughter and he refuses then we can say that it was a free action. Hence, it was a demonstration of courage and independence.

As limited as Sartre's concept of freedom is, Sartre argues that it accounts for the non-existence of God. Man, in the first instance, contrary to creationism was abandoned – a word he borrowed from Heidegger. "And when we speak of "abandonment" – a favorite word of Heidegger – we mean to say that God does not exist, and that it is necessary to draw the consequence of his absence to the end" (Sartre, *Existentialism*, 636). Human beings after being thrown into the world do not bother themselves with their history or origin as Hegel conceived, but merely start creating their essences; since there is no fixed nature or God to determine their essences. This absolute expression of freedom negates the existence of God; for freedom is incompatible with the existence of God. The very fact that there is absolute human freedom is a pointer to the non-existence of God. Thus, God not only does not de facto exist, he really cannot exist. The idea of God is a contradiction (Miceli, 223). "Everything happens as if the world, man, and man-in-the-world succeeded in realizing only a missing God. Everything happens therefore as if the in-itself and the for-itself were presented in a state of disintegration in relation to an ideal synthesis" (Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, 623).

Finally, Sartre admitted morality as a form of original sin. "Thus, original sin is my upsurge in a world where there are others; and whatever may be my further relations with others, these relations will be only variations on the original theme of my guilt" (Sartre, *Being and Nothingness*, 410). In the Novel *Nausea*, Sartre attacked the bourgeoisie for thinking that there are fixed laws and moral values like the law of gravity that govern

societies. Moral laws and values come from and within human being. He argues that human beings should take responsibility for their exercises of freedom. One is said to have acted morally when he/she abandons all fixed moral principles and categories, all self-deceptions, bad faith and inauthenticity to make his/ her choices with the consciousness that he or she is an absolutely free being, and to act otherwise is to act in bad faith.

Comparative Analysis

What has emerged from our discussions so far is the obvious fact that Nietzsche's death of God and Sartre's non-existence of God are one and the same argument both in content, and intent, except the slight cosmetic differences in terminology and the logical structures of their arguments. First, as to the origin of God, we discover that in Nietzsche, God is a product of man born out of the psychological and existential need for Dasein to give an epistemic account of the nauseated pain and despair that he or she often experience. Similarly, in Sartre, God is a product of man born out of the existential need to assert his freedom and autonomy. The illusory concept 'God' in Sartre becomes a ladder for for-itself to climb and attain his or her ultimate goal of becoming God – That is, of actualizing his freedom and autonomy, just as in Nietzsche the death of God is a ladder to actualizing the ultimate human goal of becoming superman. The point made by both Nietzsche and Sartre is that God does not even exist in content. No wonder Kurt Rudolf Fischer in his article "The Existentialism of Nietzsche's Zarathustra" argues that "Sartre's presentation resembles Nietzsche's as far as the conclusion reached on the basis of this self-image are concerned" (1004). Again, both Nietzsche and Sartre believe in the existential man or for the purpose of avoiding criticism from feminists we maintain the word 'for-itself' or human being. Not just do they believe in the existential human being, they also believe that the absence of God ushers in absolute freedom. Hence, the death of God in Nietzsche connotes the birth of human freedom, just as absolute human freedom is implied in Sartre's non-God-thesis.

To show the degree of semblance between the two non-theistic philosophies, we even observe that just as Nietzsche employed the madman's imagery in *The Gay Science*, so also Sartre employed the madman's aphorism in his play *The Devil and the Good Lord*, the madman speaks: Heinrich, I am going to tell you a colossal joke: God doesn't exist" (Sartre, cited in Fischer, 1006). In fact, to make it worse we may even adopt our previous remarks about Nietzsche pertaining to why he employs the madman's imagery and apply it to Sartre – we mean the fact that he wanted to reduce the level of attacks or criticisms against him. Perhaps the only difference is the fact that human beings are not the murderers of God in Sartre as they are portrayed in Nietzsche. Nietzsche and Sartre are both non-theistic existentialists. They both

argue that existence precedes essence. Human beings must first exist; then create his or her essence. The implication is that both of them rejected any system of fixed principle – there are no fixed human nature including circular or prescriptive morality. However, while Nietzsche appears to be very particular with the Christian doctrine and few other religions which he referred to as nihilistic doctrines, Sartre attacked fixed moral principles from a more general pedestal. The best of human beings can only be achieved when people act and think in a vacuum. This is exactly the meaning of the exercise of freedom. Another significant difference between both philosophies is in the area of societal influence. Whereas Nietzsche saw in the Athenian and German cultures the Dionysian spirit which he could build on to demonstrate the death of God and the birth of the superman, Sartre saw in the French revolutionary culture and in Husserl's philosophy the concept of consciousness which became the bedrock of his philosophy in general and rejection of the God-thesis and assertion of human freedom in particular. Again, Sartre's missing God tends to corroborate or have a semblance with Nietzsche's death of God, as God appears to have created man and died for man to develop his full potentials and assert his freedom. It is clear that neither Nietzsche nor Sartre had a soft spot for any system of fixed principle, hence; their failures to state or admit the God-cause principle. Note also that Sartre like Nietzsche, rejected traditional morality though unlike Nietzsche, Sartre admitted morality as a form of original sin.

No matter our analysis and scholars or authors beliefs, our readers should not be misled to thinking or believing that either the arguments advanced by Nietzsche on the death of God or those advanced by Sartre on the non-existence of God sufficiently succeeds in eradicating or eliminating the ontological ((conceptual) notion of God from human consciousness, rather let it be noted that both Nietzsche and Sartre saw the human over-reliance and dependence on the God-figure as a problem to human existence, hence the death of God and the non-existence of God are ways of restoring humanity to her pride of place where human freedom and autonomy are secured. In effect, what they have done is to declare God dead (Nietzsche) and declare God non-existent (Sartre) and then assigned the place and role of God to man such that the concept 'God' indirectly surges on. It must be conceded that Nietzsche's prophecies as to the future have so far proved more nearly right than those of liberals or socialists (Russell, 1962). We strongly think that their efforts are worthwhile, as human beings must learn to rely on his or her powers and abilities.

Conclusion

The very forceful, emotional and psychological nature of God-thesis or religion has influenced for-itself

not to ask fundamental questions pertaining to the truism and existential reality of God. However, Nietzsche and Sartre represent the group of philosophers that summoned the courage to ask fundamental questions based on the ontological and categorical imperative of duty. Nietzsche saw in the Athenian and German cultures the Dionysian spirit needed to restore human beings from the shackles of psychological prison that the God-thesis or religion has placed them. On the other hand, Sartre saw in the French revolutionary spirit of freedom the consciousness needed to save humanity from the over-bearing influence of religion. The content of their philosophies is the rejection of the God-thesis, as human existence is incompatible with the concept of God. In this work we have demonstrated that the central and unifying themes of Nietzschean and Sartrean philosophies are the rejection of God-thesis and the affirmation of human freedom or independence. The Death of God and non-existence of God does not refer to the death or absence of a physiological entity known as God, but the demise and absence of a psychological entity who is a product of man's existential need. Our analysis has shown that Nietzsche's death of God and Sartre's non-existence of God are one and the same both in content and intent, as their intention was to save human beings and restore her independence. These accounts for the reason they are grouped together by philosophers as existentialists and atheists.

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